

Spectrophotometric methods for the assay of fluvoxamine maleate using chromogenic reagents

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Abstract : Simple, accurate and reproducible UV-Visible spectrophotometric methods were established for the assay of fluvoxamine maleate (FXA) based on the oxidative coupling and condensation reactions. Oxidative coupling of the FXA with Brucine- IO_4^- in Method A, oxidative coupling of FXA with 2,6-dichloroquinone-4-chlorimide (DCQC) in Method B and condensation of FXA with *p*-dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde (PDAC) in Method C have been developed. The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity for the Methods (A-C) are given. Regression analysis using the method of least squares was made to evaluate the slope (*b*), intercept (*a*) and correlation coefficient (*r*) and standard error of estimation (S_e) for each system. Determination of FXA in bulk form and in pharmaceutical formulations were also incorporated. The methods have been applied for the determination of FXA in bulk form and in pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords : Estimation, fluvoxamine, precipitating agent, charge transfer complex.

Introduction

Fluvoxamine¹ (as maleate FXA) is a selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor (SSRI) used to treat obsessive compulsive disorder (OCD). It may also be used to treat depression and other conditions. It belongs to a new chemical series of 2-aminoethyloxime ethers.

The mechanism of action of fluvoxamine maleate in obsessive compulsive disorder is presumed to be linked to its specific serotonin reuptake inhibition in brain neurons. In preclinical studies, it was found that fluvoximine inhibited neuronal uptake of serotonin.

A very few physico-chemical methods appeared in the literature for the assay of FXA in biological fluids and pharmaceutical formulations. Most of them are based on visible spectrophotometric methods^{2,3}, HPLC⁴⁻⁸, GC^{9,10}, fluorimetry¹¹⁻¹³, LC-MS¹⁴, GC-MS¹⁵⁻¹⁷, TLC¹⁸ and Mass¹⁹. The analytically useful functional groups in FXA²⁰ have not been fully exploited for designing suitable, visible spectrophotometric methods. There is still a scope to develop visible spectrophotometric methods with better sensitivity, selectivity, precision and accuracy. We have developed spectrophotometric methods based on oxidative coupling of FXA with Brucine- IO_4^- in Method A, with DCQC in Method B and with PDAC in Method C.

These methods have been extended to pharmaceutical formulations as well (Table 2).

Experimental

An Elico, UV-Visible digital spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched quartz cells were used for the spectral and absorbance measurements. An Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. The commercially available formulations such as fluvoxin, soreset, Uvox and Luvox tablets (50 mg and 100 mg) from SUN, SOLUS and SOLVAY companies were taken.

All the chemicals and reagents used were analytical grade and the aqueous solutions were freshly prepared in triple distilled water. The stock solution of FXA (1 mg/ml) was prepared in 0.1 N HCl. Brucine solution (Loba; 0.2%, 5.067×10^{-3} M), NaIO_4 solution (BDH; 0.2%, 9.35×10^{-3} M), H_2SO_4 solution (Qualigens, 2.3 M) were prepared for Method A. 2,6-Dichloroquinone-4-chlorimide (DCQC) solution (BDH; 0.04%, 1.9×10^{-3} M), buffer solution (pH 9.4) were prepared for Method B. *p*-Dimethylaminocinnamaldehyde (PDAC) (BDH; 0.4%, 2.63×10^{-3} M), H_2SO_4 (Merck) were prepared for Method C.

Table 1. Optical and regression characteristics, precision and accuracy of the proposed methods for FXA

Parameter	Method A	Method B	Method C
λ_{\max} (nm)	520	460	540
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	25-150	10-60	20-120
Detection limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	7.081	2.565	4.790
Molar absorptivity ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	8.862×10^2	5.628×10^2	1.32×10^3
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ / 0.001 absorbance unit)	0.6155	0.3012	1.464×10^{-1}
Optimum photometric range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	40-125	126-250	
Regression equation ($Y = a + bc^a$)			31.62-112.2
Slope (b)	0.0101	0.012077	
Standard deviation on slope (S_b)	5.452×10^{-3}	1.5021×10^{-4}	8.889×10^{-3}
Intercept (a)	8.249×10^{-3}	6.25×10^{-3}	1.056×10^{-3}
Standard deviation on intercept (S_a)	4.520×10^{-3}	4.983×10^{-3}	4.499×10^{-3}
Standard error on estimation (S_e)	4.310×10^{-3}	4.751×10^{-3}	7.010×10^{-2}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9989	0.9997	6.685×10^{-2}
Relative standard deviation (%)	0.2041	1.359	0.9994
0.05 level	1.06	1.563	0.3564
0.01 level	1.36	2.450	1.642
% error in bulk samples	0.10	0.102	2.892
^a Six replicate analysis.			0.312

Table 2. Assay of FXA in pharmaceutical formulations

Formulation	Amount taken (mg)	Amount found by proposed methods			Reference method	Percentage recovery by proposed methods		
		Method A	Method B	Method C		Method A	Method B	Method C
Tablet I	100	99.83 ± 0.49	100.01 ± 0.45	100.03 ± 0.43	99.55 ± 0.57	99.94 ± 0.25	99.95 ± 0.11	99.93 ± 0.32
Fluoxin		F = 1.353 t = 0.915	F = 1.604 t = 1.562	F = 1.757 t = 1.162				
Tablet II	100	99.61 ± 0.43	99.69 ± 0.69	100.02 ± 0.58	99.82 ± 0.81	99.93 ± 0.32	99.95 ± 0.23	99.96 ± 0.17
Sorest		F = 3.548 t = 0.585	F = 1.3780 t = 0.3002	F = 1.9503 t = 0.473				
Tablet III	100	99.73 ± 0.34	99.64 ± 0.41	99.83 ± 0.46	99.96 ± 0.65	99.94 ± 0.26	99.92 ± 0.16	99.94 ± 0.15
Uvox		F = 3.654 t = 0.8047	F = 2.513 t = 1.045	F = 1.996 t = 0.405				
Tablet IV	100	99.52 ± 0.47	99.69 ± 0.31	99.53 ± 0.42	99.94 ± 0.59	99.96 ± 0.31	99.71 ± 0.14	99.94 ± 0.25
Luvox		F = 1.575 t = 1.372	F = 3.622 t = 0.96	F = 1.973 t = 1.4				

Six independent analysis are carried out.

Theoretical t-value at 95% confidence level are 2.57.

Theoretical f-value at 95% confidence level are 5.05.

Recommended procedures :

Method A (Oxidative coupling reaction with Brucine- IO_4^-):

Aliquots of FXA solution (0.5-3.0 ml, 50-300 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were transferred into different 10 cm^3 graduated tubes. 3 cm^3 ($5.067 \times 10^{-3} M$) of brucine solution, 1.5 cm^3 (9.35

$\times 10^{-3} M$) of sodium metaperiodate solution and 2 cm^3 (2.3 M) of sulphuric acid were added to each tube and the total volume was made up to 9 cm^3 with distilled water. The tubes were thoroughly shaken and placed in a water bath at 60 °C for 15 min. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and total volume was ad-

justed to 10 cm³ with distilled water. The absorbance of each solution was measured at 520 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of FXA present in the sample was computed from the calibration graph (Fig. 2).

Method B (Oxidative coupling reaction with DCQC) :

Aliquots of standard FXA solution (0.5–3.0 ml, 20–120 µg/ml) were transferred into a series of 25 cm³ calibrated tubes. Then 5.0 cm³ of buffer (pH 9.4) and 2.0 cm³ (1.9 × 10⁻³ M) of DCQC were added successively, mixed well and kept aside for 10 min and diluted up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the colored solution was measured at 460 nm against a reagent blank prepared simultaneously. The amount of FXA in the sample solution was computed from the appropriate calibration graph (Fig. 3).

Method C (Condensation with PDAC) :

To each one of 10 ml calibrated tubes, aliquots (0.5–2.5 ml, 50–250 µg/ml) of ethanolic standard drug solution 2.0 cm³ of PDAC and 3.0 cm³ of conc. H₂SO₄ were added successively and the total volume in each flask was brought to 9 cm³ by addition of CH₃OH and placed in hot water bath for 25 min. Then the flasks were cooled and made up to the mark with CH₃OH and the absorbances were measured after 5 min at 540 nm against a reagent blank prepared in a similar way (Fig. 4).

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of fluvoxamine maleate.

(Z)-But-2-enedioic acid (OR) (E)-5-methoxy-1-[4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl]pentan-1-one-O-2-aminomethyl)-oxime maleate

Fig. 2. Absorption spectrum of FXA-(Brucine-IO₄⁻): (■) reagent blank vs distilled water and (●) test vs reagent blank.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectrum of FXA-(DCQC).

Fig. 4. Absorption spectrum of FXA-(PDAC).

Results and discussion

The optimum conditions for the color development of Methods A, B and C were established by varying the parameters one at a time, keeping the others fixed and observing the effect produced on the absorbance of the colored species. The stability period of the coloured species is 1–45 min in Method A, 1–30 min in Method B and 5–60 min in Method C. The absorbance of the coloured species was gradually lowered with time.

The precision of the method to the drug was found by measuring the absorbance of 6 separate samples containing known amounts of drug and the results obtained are incorporated in Table 1. Regression analysis using the method of least squares was made to evaluate the slope (*b*), intercept (*a*) and correlation coefficient (*r*) and stan-

standard error of estimation (S_e) for each system.

The accuracy of the methods was ascertained by comparing the results by proposed and reference methods statistically by the t- and F-tests. The comparison shows that there is no significant difference between the results of studied methods and those of the reference ones. The similarity of the results is an evidence that during the application of these methods, the excipients usually present in pharmaceutical formulations do not interfere in the assay of proposed methods. As an additional check of accuracy of the proposed methods, recovery experiments were carried out. The recovery of the added amounts of standard drug were studied at 3 different levels. Each level was repeated for 6 times. From the amount of drug found, the % recovery was calculated in the usual way.

The higher λ_{\max} values of all the proposed methods have a decisive advantage since the interference from the associated ingredients should be generally less at higher wavelengths than at lower wavelengths. Thus the proposed visible spectrophotometric methods are simple and sensitive with reasonable precision, accuracy and constitute better alternatives to the existing ones to the routine determination of FXA in bulk forms and pharmaceutical formulations.

Conclusions :

The proposed methods exploit the various functional groups in FXA molecule. The decreasing order of sensitivity (ϵ_{\max}) among the proposed methods are (Method B > Method A > Method C) respectively. The concomitants which do not contain the functional groups chosen in the present investigation do not interfere in the color development by proposed methods. Thus the proposed methods are simple, sensitive and selective with reasonable precision and accuracy and constitute better alternatives to the reported ones in the assay of FXA in bulk form and pharmaceutical formulations (Table 2).

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